

Potentiometric Study of Uranyl Complexes of *o*-Hydroxy Acetophenone Oxime and its Substituted Derivatives.

D. B. INGLE and D. D. KHANOLKAR

Department of Chemistry, Marathwada University, Aurangabad

Manuscript received 10 May 1972; revised 23 December 1972; accepted 12 January 1973

The metal-ligand stability constants of uranyl ion with substituted *o*-hydroxyacetophenone oximes (OHAPOs) have been determined by the Bjerrum-Calvin pH titration technique as adopted by Irving and Rossotti. An aqueous dioxane medium containing 75% dioxane by volume and 0.1 M NaClO₂ was used. The linear relations between metal-ligand stability constants and proton, ligand stability constants were examined.

WORK on stability constants of uranyl complexes of tartarate¹, citrate², lactate³, malate²⁻⁴ and salicylate⁵ has been reported in the literature. Foley and Anderson⁶ and Rajan and Martell⁷ have shown the existence of only 1:1 uranyl-sulphosalicylate complex in aqueous solution. Banks and Singh⁸ on the other hand, obtained 1:1 and 1:2 complexes of the same system at pH 4.5 and 7.5 respectively. Some workers⁹ have reported formation of complexes of *o*-hydroxyacetophenone oxime and resacetophenone oxime in solution with a few transition metals. The present paper deals with a systematic study of stability constants of some substituted *o*-hydroxyacetophenone oximes with uranyl ion.

Experimental

Materials:

Dioxane: Dioxane (AnalaR, B.D.H.) was further purified by the method described by Vogel¹⁰ and stored out of contact with air.

Water: Distilled water was redistilled after adding alkaline permanganate in an all-glass apparatus, distillate boiled to expel carbon dioxide, cooled and stored in a well stoppered Pyrex flask.

Preparation of chelating reagents: The ligands *o*-hydroxyacetophenone oxime and its 5-methyl, 3-methyl, 5-chloro, 3-chloro, 5-bromo, 3-bromo, 5-iodo, 5-nitro and 4-hydroxy derivatives were prepared by known methods¹¹⁻²¹. The purity of the oximes was ascertained from the sharp melting points and determination of nitrogen content by Kjeldahl method.

Solutions of the complexing agents: 0.016M solutions of the reagents were prepared by dissolving the requisite quantity of the compound in pure dioxane. These solutions were protected from the action of light.

Sodium perchlorate solution: 0.8M sodium perchlorate solution was prepared by dissolving an appropriate amount of the sample (Riedel, Pure, Germany) in a known volume of carbon dioxide-free distilled water.

Metal salt solution: A solution of uranyl nitrate (AnalaR, B.D.H.) was prepared in perchloric acid solution of desired normality.

Apparatus: For pH determinations Leeds and Northrup, pH indicator (No. 7666) was employed in combination with Leeds-Northrup, std. 1199-30 glass electrode and std. 1199-31 saturated calomel electrode. This was calibrated using standard buffer solutions (pH 4 and 9).

Bjerrum-Calvin titration: The titration vessel of 150 ml capacity was dipped more than two thirds in water contained in a 1 lit glass vessel. Water at fixed temperature, pumped from an ultra-thermostat manufactured by veb-Prufgerate-werk Medingen Dresden (Germany), was continuously circulated through metallic coils immersed in the glass vessel. The temperature was maintained constant at 30° ± 0.1°, during the entire course of the titration. The titrations were carried out in an inert atmosphere by bubbling 'oxygen free' nitrogen gas through the solution in the titrations vessel in order to expel dissolved oxygen and carbon dioxide from the solution and also to stir it. Rapid mixing was achieved by magnetic stirring which was discontinued when the pH was being recorded.

Fig. 1. Plot of Log K₁ vs Log P K₂^H for UO₂(II)-Complexes of OHAPOs.

The experimental procedure involved potentiometric titrations of (i) HClO_4 ($9.2 \times 10^{-3}M$), (ii) HClO_4 ($9.2 \times 10^{-3}M$)+reagent ($2 \times 10^{-3}M$), (iii) HClO_4 ($9.2 \times 10^{-3}M$)+reagent ($2 \times 10^{-3}M$)+uranyl ion ($5 \times 10^{-4}M$) and (iv) HClO_4 +uranyl ion ($5 \times 10^{-4}M$) against standard sodium hydroxide solution ($0.2M$) added from a burette. The ionic strength of the solution was maintained constant at $0.1M$ by addition of sodium perchlorate solution. An aqueous dioxane medium containing 75% dioxane by volume was used.

Results and Discussion

The departure of the metal-ligand titration curve from the reagent curve commences from pH meter reading $B = 2.75$. The variation of \bar{n} was continuous and symmetrical upto $B = 4$ and then changed abruptly. The highest value of \bar{n} was 1.8 before the precipitation occurred. The formation of 1:2 complex took place in the region of hydrolysis of the uranyl ion. The value of $\log K_1K_2$ was obtained by the method of least squares²² which gives best approximate values and $\log K_1$ was then calculated by the pointwise calculation method²³ which agrees with that calculated by half-integral method. $\log K_2$ (tentative value) was obtained as a difference of the two values.

The stability constant values of $\log K_1$ and $\log K_2$ determined from potentiometric measurements for 1:1 and 1:2 uranyl complexes of *o*-hydroxyacetophenone oxime (OHAPO) and substituted OHAPOs are listed in table 1 alongwith the proton-ligand stability constants. The $\log K_2$ values are tentative and less reliable since the formation of 1:2 complex is observed in the region of hydrolysis of the uranyl ion.

and did not follow a linear relation. The linear relation between pk_{OH} and $\log K$ observed by Irving and Rossotti²⁴ for complexes of some metals with substituted oximes and substituted salicylaldehydes was attributed by May and Jones²⁵ to the fact that the study was limited to two particular groups of ligands with variation of dissociation constants within a narrow range. The observed non-linear behaviour of the uranyl complexes may be due to the wide variation of the dissociation constants of the different ligands.

The linear relation between $\log K/K_0$ and $\log K'/K'_0$, where K is metal-ligand stability constant of substituted OHAPOs, K_0 is that of OHAPO, K' is

Fig. 2. Plot of $\log K/K_0$ vs $\log K'/K'_0$ for $\text{UO}_2(\text{II})$ -Complexes of OHAPO.

the proton-ligand stability constant of substituted OHAPOs and K'_0 is that of OHAPO, suggested by May and Jones²⁵ was examined for 1:1 complexes

TABLE 1—METAL-LIGAND STABILITY CONSTANTS OF URANYL COMPLEXES

Temp. $30^\circ \pm 0.1^\circ$, $\mu \sim 0.1M$

Ligand No.	Name of the ligand	*Proton ligand stability constant $\log PK_2^H$	$\log K_1K_2$ (Method of least square)	$\log K_1$ (Pointwise calculations)	$\log K_2$ (By difference)
1.	OHAPO	11.86	21.11	10.66	10.45
2.	RAPO	11.14	18.84	10.04	8.80
3.	5-Methyl-OHAPO	12.11	20.42	10.56	9.86
4.	3-Methyl-OHAPO	12.05	20.24	10.64	9.60
5.	5-Chloro-OHAPO	11.28	19.28	10.18	9.10
6.	5-Bromo OHAPO	11.27	19.13	9.91	9.22
7.	3-Chloro-OHAPO	10.77	17.42	9.14	8.18
8.	3-Bromo-OHAPO	11.04	18.14	9.54	8.60
9.	5-Iodo-OHAPO	11.16	17.95	9.33	8.62
10.	5-Nitro-OHAPO	8.97	14.30	7.64	6.66

* The $\log PK_2^H$ values have been taken from Ph.D. thesis submitted to the Marathwada University by D. B. Ingle

Validity of $\log K = apk + b$ relation: The validity of the linear relation between $\log K$ and pk (where $\log K$ is metal-ligand stability and pk ($\log PK_2^H$) proton-ligand stability constant; a and b are constants) was examined. In Fig. 1 the values of $\log K_1$ were plotted against $\log PK_2^H$. The points corresponding to these values were widely scattered

of uranyl ion. It has been found that a single line passing through all the points cannot be drawn (Fig. 2).

References

1. E. PELIGOT, *J. Prakt. Chem.*, 1945, **35**, 153;
H. ITZIG, *Ber. Chem. Deutsch. Ges.*, 1901, **34**, 3822.

2. I. FELDMAN and J. R. HAVILL, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1954, **76**, 2114.
3. I. FELDMAN, J. R. HAVILL and W. F. NEUMAN, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1954, **76**, 4726.
4. S. HAKAMORI, *Science Reports Tohoku Imp. University*, 1931, **1**, **20**, 756; *Chem. Abs.*, 1932, **26**, 2366.
5. G. COURTOIS, *Bull. Soc. Chim. France*, 1923, **33**, 1761.
6. R. T. FOLEY and R. C. ANDERSON, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1949, **71**, 909.
7. K. S. RAJAN and A. E. MARTELL, *J. Inorg. Nuclear Chem.*, 1964, **26**, 789.
8. C. V. BANKS and R. S. SINGH, *J. Inorg. Nuclear Chem.*, 1960, **12**, 125.
9. K. A. VENKATACHALAM and M. B. KABADI, *Curr. Sci. (India)*, 1958, **27**, 337;
K. S. BHATKI, A. T. RANE and M. B. KABADI, *Proc. Symposium Chemistry of Coordination Compounds, Agra (India)*, 1959, Part III, pp. 78.
10. A. I. VOGEL, 'A Text Book of Practical Organic Chemistry'.
11. K. FRIES and W. PFFAFENDORF, *Ber.* 1910, **43**, 215.
12. I. HEILBRON, A. H. COOK, H. M. BUNBURY and D. H. HEY, 'Dictionary of Organic Compounds', Fourth edition, 1965, London, Eyre and Spottiswoode, Vol. 3, page 1639.
13. Ref. 12, *ibid.*, page 1717.
14. Ref. 12, *ibid.*, page 1717.
15. Ref. 12, *ibid.*, Vol. 2, page 632.
16. A. B. SEN and M. S. SAXENA, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1958, **35**, 136;
N. M. SHAH and S. R. PARIKH, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1959, **36**, 784.
17. I. HEILBRON, A. H. COOK, H. M. BUNBURY and D. H. HEY, 'Dictionary of Organic Compounds', Fourth edition, 1965, London, Eyre and Spottiswoode, Vol. 1, Page 448.
18. S. H. DANDEGAONKAR and G. R. REVANKAR, *Montash*, 1965, **96**(2), 450.
19. C. T. CHANG, F. C. CHEN, T. S. CHEN, K. K. HSU, T. UENG and M. HUNG, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1961, 3414.
20. S. S. JOSHI and HARI SINGH, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1954, **19**, 4993.
21. W. BAKER, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1934, 1691;
D. R. NADKARNI and T. S. WHEELER, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1936, 589.
22. J. B. SCARBOROUGH, 'Numerical Mathematical Analysis', Oxford University Press, 1930, page 364.
23. H. Z. HEASON and J. B. GILBERT, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1955, **77**, 2594.
24. H. IRVING and H. S. ROSSOTTI, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1954, 2910.
25. M. MAY and W. R. JONES, *J. Inorg. Nuclear Chem.*, 1962, **24**, 511; 1963, **25**, 507.